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TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR AND CONTINUANCE COMMITMENT IN THE RIVERS STATE CIVIL SERVICE

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment. A sample of 185 randomly selected managerial and non-managerial employees from ten (10) purposively drawn major Oil and Gas companies in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. A quasi-experimental research design was used, and data were collected through a cross-sectional survey using a questionnaire. The Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 15 was used for data analysis. The findings indicated the existence of a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between leaders' transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment in the Nigerian Oil and Gas industry. Specifically, leaders' idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration were revealed to have a strong positive and statistically significant influence on the employees' personal sacrifices and low alternatives in the Nigerian Oil and Gas industry. Based on these findings, the study concludes that leaders' transformational leadership behaviour plays a significant role in enhancing continuance commitment in the Nigerian Oil and Gas industry. Specifically, leaders' idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration play a significant role in enhancing the employees' personal sacrifices and low alternatives in the Nigerian Oil and Gas industry. Other theoretical and practical implications for enhancing employees' continuance commitment in the Nigerian workplace are presented.

Keywords

Transformational Leadership Behaviour, Continuance Commitment, Organizational Commitment, Civil Service, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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CONTEXT OF THE PROBLEM

Traditionally, it is argued that the factors of production are, land, labour, and capital, and more recently, entrepreneurship has been added to the list. Conventional wisdom also dictates that the most valuable and indispensable factor organizations need to run smoothly, effectively and efficiently, is the human resource (Msadragh, 2003) as it occupies two major slots (labour and entrepreneurship) on the list of factors needed to achieve production effectiveness and efficiency. Well-qualified and capable personnel are important in the context of achieving the goals and objectives of an organization. Hence, it can be argued, and rightly too, that the success of an organization depends to a large extent on the hard-working, loyal and involved managers and employees. In the modern era where the world has become a global village, organisations are considered to be competitive based on the competence of their human resource.

Organizational commitment (OC) is an important issue that has been and will remain of great importance to business organizations. Organizations are always searching for committed human resources to achieve their strategic objectives. As noted by Moris and Sherman (1981) organizational commitment is an indicator of employee performance and turnover. It helps organizations to attain their goals as it is the psychological bond between the individuals and the organization (Mowday and Mc Cade, 1979). It is the relative strength of an employee's identification with and involvement within an organization (Mowday et al, 1982 Porter et al 1974). Mayer and Allen (1979) subdivided the concept of commitment into three parts: Affective, Continuance and normative commitment. Affective commitment is an attachment that arises from the emotions of employees slowly and naturally, so it can be diffused or organic. Continuance commitment refers to commitment based on the costs that the employee associates with leaving the organization (due to the high cost of living). The individual remains with an organization because of a perceived high cost of losing organizational membership. Normative commitment is an employee's feeling of obligation to remain with the organization. The empirical evidence indicates that Organizational Commitment has important implications for employees and organizations through various studies by researchers.

The benefit of organizational commitment has been well documented in the extant management literature. Committed employees are less likely to develop patterns of tardiness or to be chronically absent from work (Angle and Perry, 1981; Bateman and Strasser, 1984; Porter 1974) Employees who are committed are also less likely to leave the organization to explore other opportunities (Allen and Meyer., 1996). Organizational commitment has also been shown to positively affect motivation, organizational citizenship, and job performance (Allen and Meyer 2002). Benneth and Durkin (2000) found that the negative effects associated with a lack of employee commitment include absenteeism and turnover.

As suggested by Drucker (1999), organizations are now evolving toward structures in which rank means responsibility but not authority, and where the supervisor's job is not to command, but to persuade. Hence, to be effective, managers must influence their subordinates, peers, and superiors to assist and support their proposals, and plans, and to motivate them to carry with their decisions (Blickle, 2003). Organizations need to know what are the aspects that play important roles or have a big impact in boosting both the performance and commitment of the employees. Swanepoel, et al (2000) highlighted that leadership styles that encourage employee commitment are essential for an organization to successfully implement business strategies, achieve its goals, gain competitive advantage and optimise human capital. Previous researchers on managerial performance such as Kanter (1982) and Pavett and Lau (1983) pointed out that an important component of successful management is the ability to influence others. As such, committed employees are more motivated and dedicated towards meeting and achieving organizational goals (Pfeffer,

1998). Empirical evidence has been produced that by creating a working environment in which employees identify with the organization's values, goals and objectives, they develop a positive attitude towards their jobs, identify with their superiors and identify with their occupational /professional group. In other words, by developing employee commitment, the objective of organizational effectiveness be achieved (Seigel & Ruh, 1973; 323; Mowday, Steers & Porter, 1979:237; Lobel & St. Clair, 1992:12066; Therenou, 1993:2832).

One major factor that must be emphasized in the effort to boost employees' commitment is the managerial leadership style. In the literature, leadership is considered the most important issue in managing and controlling organizational resources such as Human resources, Material, Capital, Finance and other basic resources and, can be observed as managerial perspectives, attitudes, behaviours, characteristics, and skills (Alkhatani, 2016). Leadership is regarded as a critical factor that brings fundamental change in organizations, which will have a positive impact on employees' attitudes and behaviour (Raja & Palanichamy, 2011). In theories of leadership, it is widely known that organizations achieve their goals through effective leadership. Steward (2006) did a meta-analysis of 93 studies and found that transformational leadership exhibited a consistently positive relationship with collective performance. Zhu, Chew, and Spangler (2005) found that human-capital-enhancing human resource management fully mediated the relationship between CEO transformational leadership behaviour and subjective assessment of organizational outcomes. Although transformational leadership applies to most organizational situations, the emergence and effectiveness of such leadership may be facilitated by some contexts and inhibited by others (Gary & Krishnan, 2003). Johnson and Dipboye (2008), examine the moderating effect of task type on the effectiveness of transformational leadership through a laboratory manipulation of the content (visionary, non-visionary) and delivery (expressive, unexpressive) of a leadership speech, along with the charisma conduciveness of performance tasks. As expected, they found that visionary content and expressive delivery resulted in higher attributions of transformational leadership. It has been found that transformational leadership is positively related to the effectiveness of the leader, subordinate's effort and job satisfaction. In addition, the effects of charismatic leadership on subordinates would be different if charisma is operationalized as an individual-level phenomenon or a group-level phenomenon, and it has been shown that transformational leadership is more effective at increasing group performance than at increasing individual performance (De, G root, & Cross, 2000).

From the discussion above, it is obvious that leadership behaviour and employee commitment have received significant attention in several earlier studies. This is due to the general recognition that these variables can be the major determinants of organizational performance (Angle, 1981; Riketta, 2002) and competitive advantage. The empirical evidence suggests that leadership behaviour has a positive and critical influence on employees' commitment. Several studies have been conducted using parts of transformational and transactional leadership theories. Some studies have found that transactional leadership augments laissez-faire leadership in enhancing organizational commitment; while others have found that transformational leadership helps to augment the organizational commitment of employees (Dubinsky, Yammarino, Spangler, 1995). As organizations continue to face complex challenges from their internal and external environments, researchers and practitioners are now turning their attention to the relationship between leadership behaviour and organizational commitment both domestically and internationally. Several major studies have found a positive relationship between these two variables. (Kraut, 1970; Neman, 1974; Alley & Gould, 1975; Porter, Campon, & Smith, 1976; Gilsson & Durick, 1988; Mathieu &

Zajac, 1990; Zeffane, 1994; & Wilson, 1995) Other studies, although small in number, have been unable to demonstrate a relationship between leadership behaviour and organizational commitment. (O'Reilly & Roberts, 1978; Hampton & Dubinsky, & Skinner, 1986; & Savery, 1991). In any case, the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and employee commitment has not yet been sufficiently addressed especially in developing countries (Garg and Ramjee, 2013) and in the Nigerian work environment in particular. Therefore, more research is needed. However, there has been no known study that examined the relationship between transformational leadership behaviours and continuance commitment in general and within the Nigerian context in particular. Although transformational leadership behaviour may have been shown to influence several other outcome variables, most of these studies were carried out in the Western world and none has examined its relationship with continuance commitment. To fill this gap in the management literature, this study examines the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment in the Rivers State Civil Service

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is presented in the figure below

Source: Conceptualised by the researcher

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework Indicating the Hypothesised Relationship between Transformational Leadership Behaviour and Continuance Commitment in major Oil and Gas companies in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

As shown in Figure 1, the independent variable in this study is Transformational leadership behaviour and the dimensions of this variable adopted for this study are based on the earlier study by Avolio, (1995) and Bass, (1998). The dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour adopted for the study include idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration (Avolio, 1995; Bass, 1998). On the other hand, the

dependent variable in this study is continuance commitment. The measures of continuance adopted for this study are based on earlier studies by Hackett, Bycio, and Hausdorf, (1994); McGee and Ford, (1987); and Somers, (1993). The measures of continuance adopted for this study include personal Sacrifices and low alternatives.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR DEFINED

Burns (1978) defined transformational leaders as those who can lift followers from their petty preoccupations and rally around a common purpose to achieve things never thought possible. Transformational leadership encompasses role modelling, handling of personal relationships with subordinates, duty orientation of the manager, critical thinking, and so on (Singh & Krishnan, 2007). Transformational leaders seek to raise the consciousness of followers by appealing to higher ideals and moral values such as liberty, justice, equality, peace, and humanitarianism, and not to base emotions such as fear, greed, jealousy, or hatred (Masood, Dani, Burns, & Backhouse, 2006).

The most common facet of transformational leadership among different definitions is that of vision. There are two visionary factors: expert and analytical, and visionary and futuristic. These influence reported performance in the organizations. For example, long-term motivation (a cultural dimension) can be achieved by offering appealing visions to subordinates (Hautala, 2005). Other critical leadership competencies are strategic thinking, relationship building, execution, and people development (Neuhauser, 2007). There are five dimensions of transformational leadership – idealized influence attributed, idealized influence behaviour, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration.

Dimensions of Transformational Leadership Behaviour

Avolio, 1995 and Bass (1998) suggested the following dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour: idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

Idealize Influence:

Idealize Influence is the behaviour that is reflected by leaders showing charismatic influence personality. According to Yammarino and Dubnisky 1994 (cited in Bass, 1995), idealized influence is the key component of transformational leadership. Using idealized influence, transformational leaders act in a way that allows them to serve as role models for their subordinates. “The leaders are admired, respected, and trusted. Their subordinate identifies

them with their charismatic personality and is attracted to emulate them. Besides, idealized leadership at its core represents the highest levels of moral reasoning and perspective-taking capacity. These leaders are willing to sacrifice their gain for the good of their group and organization. They set high standards for work conduct and are a role model for those standards. They build trust in people because those who work for them know they are working towards the common good, and their sacrifices along the way are evidence of their consistency in their actions and values. Some people see the good in others first and when it is not obvious they work to build it out with concern for people.

Inspirational Motivation:

Inspirational motivation has been variously defined in the literature. Bass (1985) stated that charismatic leaders use inspirational appeals and emotional talks to arouse follower motivations to transcend self-interest for the good of the team. At a later date, Bass (1999) stated that both charisma and inspirational motivation are displayed when a leader envisions a desirable future, articulates how it can be reached, sets an example to be followed, sets high standards of performance, and shows determination and confidence. This description suggests vision and inspirational motivation might be combined into a single construct. Bass (1985) restricted the use of the term inspirational leadership to instances when a leader employs or adds nonintellectual, emotional qualities to the influence process. He stated that inspirational leaders add affective qualities to the influence process through the use of inspirational talks and emotional appeals. Similarly, Yukl (1981:121) suggested that inspiration refers to “the extent to which a leader stimulates enthusiasm among subordinates for the work of the group and says things to build subordinate confidence in their ability to perform assignments successfully and attain group objectives”.

A recurring element within existing definitions of inspirational leadership is the use of oral communication to motivate and arouse followers’ emotions. As a result, we focus on inspirational communication, or the use of appeals and emotion-laden statements to arouse followers’ emotions and motivation, as opposed to the broader construct of inspirational motivation proposed by Bass and his colleagues. In this study, we suggest that inspirational communication is a distinct construct, defined as the expression of positive and encouraging messages about the organization, and statements that build motivation and confidence.

Transformational leaders get followers involved in envisioning attractive future states; they create communicated expectations that followers want to meet and also demonstrate commitment to goals and the shared vision” (Bass and Riggio; 2006:6). Inspirational motivation is about encouragement to raise the consciousness of workers about the organization’s mission, and vision, and committing to the vision is a key theme of this factor. The key indicators of

inspirational motivation are “organizational vision, communication, challenging to workers encouragement, working with workers, and giving autonomy are the core values of inspirational motivation”

Intellectual Stimulation:

The most underdeveloped component of transformational leadership is intellectual stimulation (Lowe et al, 1996). This leadership factor encompasses behaviours that increase followers’ interest in and awareness of problems, and that develop their ability and propensity to think about problems in new ways (Bass, 1985). The effects of intellectual stimulation are seen in the increase in followers’ abilities to conceptualize, comprehend, and analyze problems and in the improved quality of solutions that they generate (Bass & Avolio, 1990).

While this leadership factor has not been the subject of extensive research, this construct encompasses a more focused, and internally consistent set of behaviours than the other sub-dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour. Intellectually stimulating leaders see the advantages of creating unity through diversity. By bringing together and integrating a diverse range of perspectives, they can create genuinely new ideas and initiatives. The goal of intellectual stimulation is to continuously generate the highest levels of creativity from the subordinates (Avolio, 2005).

Individualized Consideration:

One factor that distinguishes transformational leadership behaviour from other new leadership theories is the inclusion of individualized consideration. Bass (1985) initially stated that individualized consideration occurs when a leader has a development orientation towards staff, displays individualized attention to followers and responds appropriately to their personal needs.

More recently, discussions of individualized consideration have focused on one component of this construct, supportive leadership. For example, Avolio and Bass, (1995:202) stated “The leader displays more frequent individualized consideration by showing general support for the efforts of followers”. Other authors in the transformational leadership field have also focused on supportive leadership as opposed to the broader construct of individualized attention. Podsakoff et al. (1990) examined individualized support, which was defined as behaviour on the part of a leader that indicates that he or she respects his or her followers and is concerned with followers’ feelings and needs.

Individualized considerate leaders pay special attention to each follower’s needs for achievement and growth by acting as an advisor, coach or mentor. Subordinates and colleagues are developed successively to higher levels of potential. Individualized consideration is practised when new learning opportunities are created along with a supportive climate. Individual differences in terms of needs and desires are

recognized. The leader delegates tasks as a means of developing followers. Delegated tasks are monitored to sincerely identify if the followers need further support (Bass and Riggio, 2006).

The finding on the Impact of transformational leadership on followers' influence strategies supports the above idea in that the followers of transformational leaders experience a total and unqualified belief in and identification with the leaders and their mission. Thus, “transformational leaders are seen as helpful and friendly, and therefore followers would use friendliness strategy more frequently” (Krishnan, 2004:69).

2.2 CONTINUANCE COMMITMENT DEFINED

Researchers view organizational commitment as a multi-dimensional concept that has different factors associated with it. Allen and Meyer (1991) have been at the forefront of multi-dimensions/approaches. Their three-component model of organizational commitment is the effective, the continuance and the normative commitment. Affective commitment according to Allen and Meyer (1991) is a positive emotional attachment to the organization. According to them, employees who are affectively committed identify with the goals of the organization and desire to remain a part of the organization because he/she “wants to”. On their part, Peter et al (1974) characterize affective commitment by three factors; “belief in and acceptance of the organizations' goals and values, a willingness to focus effort on helping the organization achieve its goals, and a desire to maintain organizational membership”. The third component of organizational commitment (which is also our subject matter of interest) is the normative commitment which reflects a feeling of obligation to continue in the employment. It is based on Beckers' (1960) side bet theory which posits that as individuals remain in the organization for longer periods, they accumulate investments, which become costly to lose the longer the individual stays. In this light, Reichers (1985) sees continuance commitment as the willingness to remain in an organization because of the investment that the employee has with “non-transferable” investments such as retirements, relationships with other employees or things that are special to the organization (years of employment or benefits that the employee may receive).

Allen and Mayer (1990) explain continuance commitment as the employee committing to the organization because he/she perceives the high cost of losing organizational membership. The employee therefore remains a member of the organization because he/she “has to”. On his part, Romzek (1990) describes continuance commitment as a transactional attachment and argues that employees calculate their investment in the organization based on what they put in and what they stand to gain if they remain with the organization. In addition to the fear of losing investment, individuals develop continuance commitment because of a perceived lack of alternatives

continuance commitment therefore reflects a calculation of the cost of leaving various the benefits of staying. Allen and Meyer, (1990) see normative commitment as the employee remaining with the organization because of feelings of obligation. These feelings may derive from many sources like resources invested in training the employees, who then feel morally obliged to put more effort into the job and stay with the organization to repay the debt. However, as normative commitment may only last until the debts are regarded as paid, it is subject to be lost later on. Thus if this type of commitment is the dominating form of commitment, it will potentially only last as long as the internal or external pressure is present “or until the debt remains unpaid. Employees stay with the organization because they “ought to”. Bolon (1993) sees normative commitment as the commitment that a person believes he/she has to the organization for their feeling of obligation to their work.

Components/Measures of Continuance Commitment

Research has shown that the variable continuance commitment has two dimensions: Personal Sacrifices and Low Alternatives (Hacketh, Bycio, and Hausdorf, 1994; McGee and Ford, 1987; Somers, 1993). There is little research on antecedents of the two dimensions of continuance commitment. The theoretical rationale behind the two constructs suggests that personal sacrifice will be related to variables that represent side-bets, namely investments that might be lost if one leaves the organisation. Demographic variables such as age and tenure are considered good indicators of such side-bets (Becker, 1960). For example, older and veteran employees will hesitate to leave the organisation so as not to lose pension plans or other accumulated benefits. Conceptually, the low “alternatives” dimension represents a construct similar to withdrawal cognition and thus is expected to relate to situational variables affecting stay/leave factors like job satisfaction, perceived performance, or job tension.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

It has been found that charismatic or transformational leadership is positively related to the effectiveness of the leader, the subordinate’s effort, and job satisfaction and to the subordinate’s organizational commitment. In addition, the effects of charismatic leadership on subordinates would be different if charisma is operationalized as an individual-level phenomenon or a group-level phenomenon, and it has been shown that charismatic leadership is more effective at increasing group performance than at increasing individual performance (DeGroot, Kiker, & Cross, 2000).

Steward (2006) did a meta-analysis of 93 studies and found that transformational leadership exhibited a consistently positive relationship with collective performance. Zhu, Chew, and Spangler (2005) found that human-capital-enhancing human resource management fully mediated the relationship between CEO transformational leadership behaviour and subjective assessment of organizational outcomes. Although transformational leadership applies to most organizational situations, the emergence and effectiveness of such leadership may be facilitated by some contexts and inhibited by others (Garg &

Krishnan, 2003). Johnson and Dipboye (2008) examined the moderating effect of task type on the effectiveness of charismatic leadership through a laboratory manipulation of the content (visionary, non-visionary) and delivery (expressive, unexpressive) of a leadership speech, along with the charisma conduciveness of performance tasks. As expected, they found that visionary content and expressive delivery resulted in higher attributions of charismatic leadership. In addition, visionary content led to better quality performance on more charisma-conducive tasks.

The six main transformational leadership behaviours that relate to organizational citizenship are: articulating a vision, providing an appropriate model, fostering the acceptance of group goals, expecting high performance, and providing individualized support and intellectual stimulation. Sosik and Dinger (2007) examined the relationship between leaders' personal attributes, leadership behaviour and vision content and found that charismatic leadership was most positively associated with inspirational vision themes, whereas contingent reward leadership was most positively associated with instructional vision themes. Leaders' need for social approval, self-monitoring, and need for social power moderated these relationships.

Transformational leaders set examples to be emulated by their followers. As suggested by Burns (1978), when leaders are morally more mature, those they lead display higher moral reasoning. Authentic transformational leadership behaviour must rest on a moral foundation of legitimate values (Burns, 1978). Moral obligations are grounded in a broader conception of individuals within the community and related social norms and cultural beliefs. To be transformational, the leader has to be morally uplifting (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999). It is required of a transformational leader to bridge ethical relativism by forging a platform of common values and congruence of interests.

Transformational leaders can use the performance appraisal system as a vehicle for individualizing the development of subordinates and guiding their future career development paths. Instead of simply catering to the immediate self-interests of followers, the transformational leader broadens followers' interest towards transcending self-interests for the good of the group, by increasing awareness about the issues of consequence and increasing the need for growth and self-actualization. As building of inspiration and self-confidence is associated with transformational leadership, effort and performance from subordinates of such leaders are beyond normal expectations. Transformational leadership results in increased employee satisfaction (Waldman, Bass & Einstein, 1987).

Given that transformational leadership behaviour has been found to have a positive influence on organizational performance and various other organizational outcome variables, it is expected that the same level of influence will be extended to continuance commitment. Based on the above, the following

hypotheses are formulated to examine the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment:

Ho₁: *There is no significant relationship between idealized influence and continuance commitment(personal sacrifices and low alternatives) in the Rivers State Civil Service.*

Ho₂: *There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and continuance commitment(personal sacrifices and low alternatives) in the Rivers State Civil Service.*

Ho₃: *There is no significant relationship between intellectual stimulation and continuance commitment(personal sacrifices and low alternatives) in the Rivers State Civil Service.*

Ho₄: *There is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and continuance commitment(personal sacrifices and low alternatives) in the Rivers State Civil Service.*

RESEARCH METHODS

Operational Measures of Variables: The independent variable in this study is transformational leadership behaviour. The dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration (Avolio, 1995; Bass, 1998). Transformational leadership was measured using the transformational leadership questionnaire (TLQ) of Singh and Krishnan (2007). The scale has 30 items (Please see appendix), with six items for each of the five factors – idealized influence attributed (heroism), idealized influence behaviour (ideology), inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. The variables are measured on an ordinal scale using the 5-point Likert-type scale. The response mode ranges from 1-5; where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Not sure/neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = strongly agree.

On the other hand, the dependent variable in this study is continuance commitment. Research has shown that the variable continuance commitment has two dimensions: Personal Sacrifices and Low Alternatives (Hacketh, Bycio, and Hausdorf, 1994; McGee and Ford, 1987; Somers, 1993). Three items were used to measure each of the components of continuance commitment, making a total of 6 items in all. The variables are measured on an ordinal scale using the 5-point Likert-type scale. The response mode ranges from 1-5; where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Not sure/neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = strongly agree.

Data Analysis Techniques

To empirically evaluate the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was employed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was chosen because all the variables in the study are measured on an ordinal scale. The analysis considered the relationship between the dimensions of transformational leadership (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) and the measures of continuance commitment (personal sacrifice and low alternatives). Each of the dimensions of transformational leadership was used as an independent or predictor variable against each of the components of continuance commitment as a dependent or criterion variable.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Analysis of Questionnaire

Table 1 and Table 2 below are used to analyse the questionnaire in terms of distribution and demographic profile of respondents respectively.

Table 1 Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percent
Distributed	200	100%
Not retrieved	15	7.5 %
Retrieved	185	92.5%
Useful response	183	91.5%
Not used	2	1%

A total of two hundred (200) copies of the questionnaires were distributed. One hundred and eighty five (185) copies (representing 92.5%) were retrieved; while 15 copies (7.5%) were not retrieved. The one hundred and eighty five (185) copies representing 92.5%, a total of 183 (91.5%) proved useful and therefore used for statistical analysis. Data collected from respondents were statistically tested as indicated on the table below.

Table 2 Demographic profile of respondents

S/No	Demographic variables	No	Percent
1	Gender		
	Male	95	51.9
	Female	88	48.1
	Total	183	100.00
2	Age		
	< 20 years	19	10.3

	20 – 29 years	39	21.3
	30 – 39 years	87	47.5
	> 40 years	38	20.9
	Total	183	100.00
3	Highest Education Qualification		
	FSCL	13	7.1
	SSCE/GCC	21	11.4
	HND/B.Sc	86	46.9
	MA/M.Sc/MBA	38	20.7
	Ph.D	25	13.9
	Total	183	100.00
4	Number of years of patronage		
	<2yrs	31	16.9
	2-4yrs	47	25.6
	5-8yrs	73	39.8
	9yrs>	32	17.7
	Total	183	100.00

Table 2 above shows the information on demographic profile of respondents. The table shows that 95 respondents (51.9%) were male while 88 respondents (48.1%) were female. This implies that male respondents were of the majority.

The information on age brackets of the respondents in section 2 of Table 2 above shows that 19 respondents (10.3%) were less than 20 years, 39 respondents (21.3%) were within the age bracket of 20 – 29 years; 87 respondents (47.5%) were within the age bracket of 30 – 39 years; while 38 respondents (20.9%) were within the age bracket of greater than 40 years. This information shows that majority of the respondents were within the age bracket of 30-39 years.

Section 3 of Table 2 above shows information on the respondents' level of education. They were represented as follows: FSLC =13 representing 7.1%; SSCE/GCE=21 representing 11.4%;HND/B.SC= 86representing46.9%; MA/MSC/MBA= 38 representing 20.7%; and Ph.D =25 representing 13.9%. From the information above it shows that respondents with HND/B.SC are of the majority.

Section five of Table 2 records the number of years you have worked in the Nigerian Oil and Gas industry. The representation are as follows; less than 2yearas =31 representing 16.9%; 2-4 years = 47 representing25.6%; 5-8years 73 representing39.8%; more than 9years =32

representing 17.7%. From the information above, it shows that respondents who have worked for 5-8 years are of majority.

Reliability Analysis

The reliability of the research instrument was ascertained with Cronbach Alpha. With a value of .814 as shown in the value is above the threshold value of .7 as suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994). This shows that the measuring instrument is internally consistent and therefore suitable for the empirical study.

Statistical Testing of the Hypotheses

To ascertain the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance and other hypothesised relationships, multiple regression analysis was conducted.

Hypothesis 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Table 3-5 Multiple Regression analysis showing the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance and the effect of transformational leadership behaviour attributes on employee personal sacrifices.

Table 3 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.883 ^a	.780	.778	.24008

a. Predictors: (Constant), Individualised Consideration, Inspirational Motivation, Idealised Influence, Intellectual Stimulation

Table 4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	300.210	4	75.052	1302.084	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.260	178	.058		
	Total	310.470	182			

a. Dependent Variable: Personal Sacrifice

b. Predictors: (Constant), Individualised Consideration, Inspirational Motivation, Idealised Influence, Intellectual Stimulation

Table 3 shows that R is .883, and represents the simple correlation between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment in the Nigerian oil and gas industry is very high. R² value (“R” Square) is .780 and adjusted R square is .778. This implication is that 78% of the variance in continuance commitment can be explained by the changes in independent variables (transformational leadership behavior) in terms of idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration. As a general rule, this model is considered as a ‘good fit’ as this, linear regression model is able to explain above 60% (threshold) of variance in the dependent variable (Moosa & Hassan, 2015:102).

The p value .000 is <0.05 in Table 4 (ANOVA TABLE) is an indication that the regression model statistically significantly predicts continuance commitment which is the outcome variable. It can thus be stated that the relationship between transformational leadership behaviour and continuance commitment is very strong, positive and significant (r=.883; F = 1302.084; pv=.000<.050).

Table 5 Multiple Regression analysis showing the effect of transformational leadership behaviour attributes on employees’ Personal Sacrifices

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-.121	.061		-1.977	.050
	Idealised Influence	.569	.054	.568	10.552	.000
	Inspirational Motivation	.015	.065	.013	.229	.019
	Intellectual Stimulation	.205	.079	.185	2.581	.011
	Individualised Consideration	.273	.065	.257	4.171	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Personal Sacrifices

The result of the regression analysis (Table 5) shows that the four dimensions or attributes of transformational leadership behavior made significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable (personal sacrifices) in the oil and gas industry: idealised influence ($\beta = 0.569$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$), and individualised consideration ($\beta = 0.273$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$), intellectual stimulation ($\beta = 0.205$, $p=0.011 < 0.050$), and inspirational motivation ($\beta = 0.015$, $p=0.019 < 0.05$), considering their respective degrees of contribution. This implies that all the

dimensions of transformational leadership behavior adopted for this study made significant unique contribution to the equation.

Therefore the model can be written as:

$$\text{Personal Sacrifices} = 0.569 (\text{IDI}) + .273 (\text{IDC}) + 0.205 (\text{ITS}) + .015 (\text{IPM}) - .121.$$

The model suggest that by associating any of the four dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour the empirical model can increase the level of continuance commitment in terms of employees’ personal sacrifices in the oil and gas industry when other things remain constant. Accordingly, changes in idealised influence attributes can have the biggest influence on level of employees’ personal sacrifices in the Oil and Gas industry as its beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.569, p=0.000 < 0.05$) is the highest followed by individualised consideration ($\beta = 0.273, p=0.000 < 0.05$), intellectual stimulation ($\beta = 0.205, p=0.011 < 0.050$), and inspirational motivation ($\beta = 0.015, p=0.019 < 0.05$).

Hypothesis 5, 6, 7 and 8

Table 6 Multiple Regression analysis showing the effect of transformational leadership behaviour attributes on employee low alternatives.

Table 6 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.008	.048		-.177	.860
	Idealised Influence	.316	.042	.336	7.483	.000
	Inspirational Motivation	.126	.051	.122	2.490	.014
	Intellectual Stimulation	.368	.062	.353	5.927	.000
	Individualised Consideration	.192	.051	.193	3.755	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Low Alternatives

The result of the regression analysis shows that the four dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour made significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable (low alternatives) in the oil and gas industry: intellectual stimulation ($\beta = 0.368, p=0.000 < 0.050$), idealised influence ($\beta = 0.316, p=0.000 < 0.05$), individualised consideration ($\beta = 0.192, p=0.000 < 0.05$), and inspirational motivation ($\beta = 0.126, p=0.014 < 0.05$), considering their respective degrees of contribution. This implies that all the dimensions of

transformational leadership behaviour variables made significant unique contribution to the equation.

Therefore the model can be written as:

$$\text{Low Alternatives} = 0.368 (\text{ITS}) + 0.316 (\text{IDI}) + .192 (\text{IDC}) + + .126 (\text{IPM}) -.008.$$

The model suggest that by associating any of the four dimensions of transformational leadership behaviour the empirical model can increase the level of continuance commitment in terms of employees' low alternatives in the oil and gas industry when other things remain constant. Accordingly therefore, changes in intellectual stimulation attributes of each oil and gas company can have the biggest influence on level of employee low alternatives as its beta co-efficient ($\beta = 0.368$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$) is the highest followed by idealised influence ($\beta = 0.316$, $p=0.000 < 0.050$), individualised consideration ($\beta = 0.192$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$), and inspirational motivation ($\beta = 0.126$, $p=0.014 < 0.05$),

Testing of hypotheses 1-8

Decision Rule

If $PV < 0.05$ = Hypothesis is supported

$PV > 0.05$ = Hypothesis is not supported

H1: The outcome of analysis show that idealised influence had significant effect on employees' personal sacrifices to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = 569$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

H2: The outcome of analysis show that inspirational motivation had significant effect on employees' personal sacrifices to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .015$, $p=0.019 < 0.05$).

H3: The outcome of analysis show that intellectual stimulation had significant effect on employees' personal sacrifices to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .205$, $p=0.011 < 0.05$).

H4: The outcome of analysis show that individualised consideration had significant effect on employees' personal sacrifices to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = 273$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

H5: The outcome of analysis show that idealised influence had significant effect on employees' low alternatives to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .316$, $p=0.014 < 0.05$).

H6: The outcome of analysis show that inspirational motivation had significant effect on employees' low alternatives to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .126$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

H7: The outcome of analysis show that intellectual stimulation had significant effect on employees' low alternatives to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .368$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

H8: The outcome of analysis show that individualised consideration had significant effect on employees' low alternatives to the oil and gas companies in in Port Harcourt ($\beta = .192$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of the present study lend support to the findings of the earlier study conducted by Chen (2002) which found that both transformational and transactional leadership behaviours have a slightly positive relationship with organizational commitment. Leadership contributes significantly to the success and failure of an organization. Transformational leadership attributes-empowerment and clear vision- are often seen as important elements for employee commitment (Iverson and Roy, 1994; Sergiovanni and Corbally, 1984; Smith and Peterson, 1988). This type of leadership style is often associated with a flatter organisational structure and low power distance. On the contrary, firms which tend to be more bureaucratic and hierarchical are policy-driven and decisions are made centrally. Leadership tends to be based on position, authority and seniority. Also, commitment is highly associated with loyalty to the top boss. Redding (1990) suggested that personal relationships could command a high employee commitment. Empirical evidence has been produced on those demographic variables such as years in the organization, age of the employee, his levels of education and the duration of leadership having a significant impact on organizational commitment (Chen and Fran Cesco, 2000; Mathieu and Zajac, 1990; Salancik, 1977).

Transformational leaders set examples to be emulated by their followers. As suggested by Burns (1978), when leaders are morally more mature, those they lead display higher moral reasoning. Authentic transformational leadership behaviour must rest on a moral foundation of legitimate values (Burns, 1978). Moral obligations are grounded in a broader conception of individuals within the community and related social norms and cultural beliefs. To be

transformational, the leader has to be morally uplifting (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999). It is required of a transformational leader to bridge ethical relativism by forging a platform of common values and congruence of interests.

Romzek (1990) describes continuance commitment as a transactional attachment and argues that employees calculate their investment in the organization based on what they put in and what they stand to gain if they remain with the organization. In addition to the fear of losing investment, individuals develop continuance commitment because of a perceived lack of alternatives continuance commitment therefore reflects a calculation of the cost of leaving versus the benefits of staying. Allen and Meyer, (1990) see normative commitment as the employee remaining with the organization because of feelings of obligation. These feelings may derive from many sources like resources invested in training the employees, who then feel morally obliged to put more effort into the job and stay with the organization to repay the debt. However, as normative commitment may only last until the debts are regarded as paid, it is subject to be lost later on. Thus if this type of commitment is the dominating form of commitment, it will potentially only last as long as the internal or external pressure is present “or until the debt remains unpaid. Employees stay with the organization because they “ought to”. Bolon (1993) sees normative commitment as the commitment that a person believes he/she has to the organization for their feeling of obligation to their work.

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APPENDIX A

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR QUESTIONNAIRE (TLQ)

S/N	Idealized Influence Attributed (Heroism)	Strongly Disagree =1	Disagree =2	Not sure =3	Agree =4	strongly agree =5
1.	Makes others feel that they are important members of his/her group.					
2.	Is the epitome of confidence, whatever the situation.					
3.	Leads from the front.					
4.	Shows a tremendous amount of faith in others' abilities.					
5.	Has the courage to make bold decisions and stick to them.					
6.	Works for the group's common goal, even at the cost of foregoing personal benefits.					
Idealized Influence Behaviour (Ideology)						
1.	Exhibits consistency in behaviour when it comes to his/her set of core values.					
2.	Coordinates well between multiple fractions or subgroups.					
3.	Leads by example, by practicing what he/she preaches.					
4.	Is clear in his/her thoughts and actions					
5.	Lives up to his/her commitments, no matter what.					
6.	Influences each person not to be selfish, but to think about the comfort of others.					
Inspirational Motivation						
1.	Involves each member of his/her group in striving towards the group's common goal.					
2.	Is hardworking and enthusiastic about assignments.					
3.	Is charged with energy to do more.					
4.	Does not miss any opportunity to talk about the vision of the group or Organization					
5.	Is persistent in achieving the targets					
6.	Has a fantastic sense of visualization of future outcomes.					
Intellectual Stimulation						
1.	Encourages others to solve problems independently.					
2.	Listens to others with patience					
3.	Makes others questions the assumptions they make, for even the simplest of things.					
4.	Promotes free and radical thinking					
5.	Asks others to think in non-technical ways to arrive at solutions.					
6.	Nurtures creativity by not imposing too many processes.					
Individualized Consideration						
1.	Recognizes the fact that different people need to be treated differently.					
2.	Recognizes competence in others and encourages them to build on the same.					
3.	Not only develops others, but brings the best out of them in pressure situations.					
4.	Is sensitive to others' personal needs.					

5.	Encourages others to discuss professional as well as personal issues with him/her.					
6.	Ensure that others get all possible support so that they can pursue other interest of life.					

CONTINUANCE COMMITMENT QUESTIONNAIRE (CCQ)						
	Continuance Commitment	Strongly Disagree =1	Disagree =2	Not sure =3	Agree =4	strongly agree =5
1.	I am not afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another lined up.					
2.	It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.					
3.	Too much in my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.					
4.	It wouldn't be too costly for me to leave my organization now					
5.	Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desired.					
6.	I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.					